

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SCREENING OF INCISION WOUND MODEL USING
ALCOHOLIC EXTRACT OF VARIOUS SPECIES OF
HIBISCUS FLOWERS IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS****Amena Banu*, Varunkumar, Arshiya Naaz, Bhimabai.D, Sonali Vilas Badganchi and
Nikita Sanjeev**

Aryan College of Pharmacy - Kalaburagi

Abstract:

The present study aimed to evaluate the wound healing potential of Hibiscus plant extracts using the incision wound model in albino rats. Wound healing is a complex biological process involving inflammation, tissue formation, and remodeling. Traditional medicine has long used Hibiscus species, particularly Hibiscus rosa-sinensis, for treating wounds due to their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties.

In this study, animals were divided into three groups: control (base ointment), standard (povidone-iodine), and test (5% and 10% Hibiscus extract ointment). A standardized 6 cm incision wound was made on the dorsal surface of anesthetized rats, and treatments were applied topically once daily for 10 days. Wound healing was assessed through tensile strength measurements, histopathological analysis, and observational parameters such as wound contraction and epithelialization.

The results demonstrated that animals treated with Hibiscus extract showed significantly increased tensile strength compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$), along with improved collagen formation and faster re-epithelialization. Histological studies confirmed enhanced fibroblast proliferation and organized tissue regeneration.

These findings indicate that Hibiscus plant extract possesses significant wound healing activity, supporting its traditional use and potential as a natural therapeutic agent in wound management.

Corresponding author:**Amena Banu,**

Associate Professor,

Aryan College of Pharmacy - Kalaburagi

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press Amena Banu et al., Screening Of Incision Wound Model Using Alcoholic Extract Of Various Species Of Hibiscus Flowers In Albino Wistar Rats, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(11).

INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal herbs as potential source of therapeutic aids has attained a significant role in health system all over the world for both humans and animals not only in the diseased condition but also as potential material for maintaining proper health care.¹

The valuable medicinal properties of different plants are due to presence of several constituents i.e. Saponins, tannins, alkaloids, phenols, glyco-alkaloids, flavonoids, sesquiterpenes lactones and terpenoides.²

The essential values of some plants have long been published, but a large number of them have remained unexplored to date. Therefore, there is a necessity to explore their uses and to conduct pharmacognostic and pharmacological studies to ascertain their therapeutic properties.³

India is sitting on a gold mine of well recorded and well-practiced knowledge of traditional herbal medicine. India is one of the 12 mega biodiversity centers having over 45,000 plant species. Its diversity is unmatched due to the presence of 16 different agro climatic zones, 10 vegetative zones and 15 biotic provinces. The country has 15,000 – 18,000 flowering plants, 23,000 fungi, 2500 algae, 1600 lichens, 1800 bryophytes and 30 million microorganisms.⁴

WOUND:

Wound was probably the first medical problem faced by the human race.

Wound is nothing but an injury to living tissue caused by various factors like blow, cut or other impacts; whereas wound healing is a process of restoring damaged tissue as closely as possible to its normal state. It mainly depends on the repairing ability of the tissue, type and extent of damage and general state of the health of the tissue.⁵

The entire wound healing process starts at the moment of injury and can continue for months to years. The stages of wound healing are inflammatory phase, proliferation phase, fibroblastic phase and maturation phase⁶⁻¹⁸.

The classic model of wound healing is divided into three or four sequential, yet overlapping, phases:

- (1) Hemostasis Phase.
- (2) Inflammatory Phase.
- (3) Proliferative Phase.
- (4) Remodeling Phase.

a. HEMOSTASIS PHASE:

Upon injury to the skin, a set of complex biochemical events takes place in a loosely orchestrated cascade to repair the damage. Within minute post-injury, platelets (thrombocytes) aggregate at the injury site to form a fibrin clot. This clot acts to control active bleeding (hemostasis).¹⁹

Figure 01: Hemostasis phase of wound healing.

In the inflammatory phase, bacteria and debris are phagocytized and removed, and factors are released that cause the migration and division of cells involved in the proliferative phase.

The proliferative phase is characterized by angiogenesis, collagen deposition, granulation tissue formation, epithelialization, and wound contraction. In angiogenesis, new blood vessels are formed by vascular endothelial cells. In fibroplasia and granulation tissue formation, fibroblasts grow and form a new, provisional extracellular matrix (ECM) by excreting collagen and fibronectin. Concurrently, re-epithelialization of the epidermis occurs, in which epithelial cells proliferate and 'crawl' at top of the wound bed, providing cover for the new tissue.

In contraction, the wound is made smaller by the action of myofibroblasts, which establish a grip on the wound edges and contract themselves using mechanism similar to that in smooth muscle cells. When the cells roles are close to complete, unneeded cells undergo apoptosis.

In the maturation and remodeling phase, collagen is remodeled and realigned along tension lines and cells that are no longer needed are removed by apoptosis.

However, this process is not only complex but fragile, and susceptible to interruption or failure leading to the formation of chronic non-healing wounds. Factors which may contribute to this include diabetes, venous or arterial disease, old age, and infection.²⁰

b. INFLAMMATORY PHASE

In the inflammatory phase (lag phase/resting phase), clotting takes place in order to obtain hemostasis, or stop blood loss²¹, and various factors are released to attract cells that phagocytize debris, bacteria, and damaged tissue and release factors that initiate the proliferative phase of wound healing.²²

CLOTTING CASCADE:

When tissue is first wounded, blood comes in contact with collagen, triggering blood platelets to begin secreting inflammatory factors. Platelets also

express glycoproteins on their cell membranes that allow them to stick to one another and to aggregate, forming a mass. Fibrin and fibronectin cross-link together and form a plug that traps proteins and particles and prevents further blood loss²³. This fibrin- fibronectin plug is also the main structural support for the wound until collagen is deposited. Migratory cells use this plug as a matrix to crawl across, and platelets adhere to it and secrete factors. The clot is eventually lysed and replaced with granulation tissue and then later with collagen²⁴.

PLATELETS:

Platelets, the cells present in the highest numbers shortly after a wound occurs, release a number of things into the blood, including ECM proteins and cytokines, including growth factors. Growth factors stimulate cells to speed their rate of division. Platelets also release other pro-inflammatory factors like serotonin, bradykinin, prostaglandins, prostacyclin's, thromboxane, and histamine, which serve a number of purposes, including to increase cells proliferation and migration to the area and to cause blood vessels to become dilated and porous.²⁵

VASOCONSTRICTION AND VASODILATION:

Immediately after a blood vessel is breached, ruptured cell membranes release inflammatory factors like thromboxane and prostaglandins that cause the vessel to spasm to prevent blood loss and to collect inflammatory cells and factors in the area. This vasoconstriction lasts five to ten minutes and is followed by vasodilation, a widening of blood vessels, which peaks at about 20 minutes post-wounding. Vasodilation is the result of factors released by platelets and other cells. The main factor involved in causing vasodilation is histamine. Histamine also causes blood vessels to become porous, allowing the tissue to become edematous because proteins from the bloodstream leak into the extravascular space, which increases its osmolar load and draws water into the area. Increased porosity of blood vessels also facilitates the entry of inflammatory cells like leukocytes into the wound site from the bloodstream.²⁶⁻²⁹

POLYMORPHONUCLEAR

NEUTROPHILS:

Within an hour of wounding, poly-morphonuclear neutrophils (PMNs) arrive at the wound site and become the predominant cells in the wound for the first two days after the injury occurs, with especially high numbers on the second day. They are attracted to the site by fibronectin, growth factors, and substances such as kinins.

Neutrophils phagocytose debris and bacteria and also kill bacteria by releasing free radicals what is called a 'respiratory burst', they also cleanse the wound by secreting proteases that break down damaged tissue. Neutrophils usually undergo

apoptosis once they have completed their tasks and are engulfed and degraded by macrophages. Other leukocytes to enter the area include helper T cells, which secrete cytokines to cause more T cells to divide and to increase inflammation and enhance vasodilation and vessel permeability. T cells also increase the activity of macrophages.³⁰

MACROPHAGES:

Macrophages are essential to wound healing. They replace PMNs as the predominant cells in the wound by two days after injury. Attracted to the wound site by growth factors released by platelets and other cells, monocytes from the bloodstream enter the area through blood vessels walls. Number of monocytes in the wound peak one to one and half days after the injury occurs. Once they are in the wound site, monocytes mature in to microphages. Recently it has been found that the spleen contains half the body's monocytes in reserve ready to deployed to injured tissue. The macrophage's main role is to phagocytise bacteria and damaged tissue, and it also debrides damaged tissue by releasing proteases. Macrophages also secrete a number of factors such as growth factors and other cytokines, especially during the third and fourth post-wounding days. These factors attract cells involved in the proliferation stage of healing to the area

Macrophages are stimulated by the low oxygen content of their surroundings to produce factors that induce and speed angiogenesis, and they also stimulate cells that re-epithelialize the wound, create granulation tissue, and lay down a new extracellular matrix. By secreting these factors, macrophages contributes in pushing the wound healing process into the next phase.³¹

DECLINE OF INFLAMMATORY PHASE:

As inflammation dies down, fewer inflammatory factors are secreted, existing ones are broken down, and number of neutrophils and macrophages are reduced at the wound site. These changes indicate that the inflammatory phase is ending and the proliferative phase is underway.³²

FIGURE 02: INFLAMMATORY PHASE OF WOUND HEALING

c. PROLIFERATIVE PHASE:

Above two or three days after the wound occurs, fibroblasts begin to enter the wound site, marking the onset of the proliferative phase even before the inflammatory phase has ended.³³

As in the order phases of wound healing, steps in the proliferative phase do not occur in a series but rather partially overlap in time. *The proliferative phase is called the reconstruction.*³⁴

ANGIOGENESIS:

Also called neovascularization, the process of angiogenesis occurs concurrently with fibroblast proliferation when endothelial cells migrate to the area of the wound. Because the activity of fibroblasts and epithelial cells requires oxygen and nutrients, angiogenesis is imperative for other stages in wound healing, like epidermal and fibroblast migration. The tissue in which angiogenesis has occurred typically looks red (erythematous) due to the presence of capillaries. Stem cells of endothelial cells, originating from of uninjured blood vessels, develop pseudopodia and push through the ECM into the wound site to establish new blood vessels.³⁵⁻³⁸

Endothelial cells are attracted to the wound area by fibronectin found on the fibrin scab and chemotactically by angiogenic factors released by other cells, e.g. from macrophages and platelets when in a low oxygen environment. Endothelial growth and proliferation is also directly stimulated by hypoxia, and presence of lactic acid in the wound.

To migrate, endothelial cells need collagenases and plasminogen activator to degrade the clot and part of the ECM. Zinc-dependent metalloproteinase digest basement membrane and ECM to allow cell migration, proliferation and angiogenesis. When macrophages and other growth factor-producing cells are no longer in a hypoxic, lactic acid-filled environment, they stop producing angiogenic factors. Thus, when tissue is adequately perfused, migration and proliferation of endothelial cells is reduced. Eventually blood vessels that are no longer needed die by apoptosis. **FIBROPLASIA AND**

GRANULATION TISSUE FORMATION:

Simultaneously with angiogenesis, fibroblasts begin accumulating in the wound site. Fibroblasts begin entering the wound site two to five days after wounding as the inflammatory phase is ending, and their numbers peak at one to two weeks post wounding. By the end of the first week, fibroblasts are the main cells in the wound. Fibroplasia ends two to four weeks after wounding.

In the first two or three days after injury, fibroblasts mainly proliferate and migrate, while

later, they are the main cells that lay down the collagen matrix in the wound site. Fibroblasts from normal tissue migrate into the wound area from its margins. Initially fibroblasts use the fibrin scab formed in the inflammatory phase to migrate across, adhering to fibronectin. Fibroblasts then deposit ground substance into the wound bed, and later collagen, which they can adhere for migration.³⁹

GRANULATION TISSUE:

Functions as rudimentary tissue, and begins to appear in the wound already during the inflammatory phase; two to five days post wounding, and continues growing until the wound bed is covered. Granulation tissue consists of new blood vessels, fibroblasts, inflammatory cells, endothelial cells, myofibroblasts, and the components of a new, provisional extracellular matrix (ECM).⁴⁰

The provisional ECM is different in composition from the ECM in normal tissue and its components originate from fibroblasts. Such components include fibronectin, collagen, glycosaminoglycans, elastin, glycoproteins and proteoglycans. Its main components are fibronectin and hyaluronase, which create a much hydrated matrix and facilitate cell migration. Later this provisional matrix is replaced with an ECM that more closely resembles that found in non-injured tissue.⁴¹

Growth factors (PDGF, TGF- β) and fibronectin encourage proliferation, migration to the wound bed, and production of ECM molecules by fibroblasts. Fibroblast also secretes growth factors that attract epithelial cells to the wound site. Hypoxia also contributes to fibroblast proliferation and excretion of growth factors, though too little oxygen will inhibit their growth and deposition of ECM components, and can lead to excessive, fibrotic scarring.

COLLAGEN DEPOSITION:

Once of fibroblasts most important duties is the production of collagen. Fibroblasts begin secreting appreciable collagen by the second or third post-wounding day, and its deposition peaks at one to three weeks. Collagen production continues rapidly for two to four weeks, after which its destruction matches its production and so its growth levels off.

Collagen deposition is important because it increases the strength of the wound; before it is laid down, the only thing holding the wound closed is the fibrin- fibronectin clot, which does not provide much resistance to traumatic injury. Also, cells involved in inflammation, angiogenesis on the collagen matrix laid down by fibroblasts.

Even as fibroblast producing new collagen, collagenases and other factors degrade it. Shortly after wounding, synthesis exceeds degradation level so collagen levels in the wound rise, but later production and degradation become equal so there is no net collagen gain. This homeostasis signals the onset of the maturation phase. Granulation gradually ceases and fibroblasts decrease in number in the wound once their work is done. At the end of the granulation phase, fibroblasts begin to commit apoptosis, converting granulation tissue from an environment rich in cells to one that consists mainly of collagen.

EPITHELIALIZATION:

The formation of granulation tissue in an open wound allows the re-epithelialization phase to take place, as epithelial cells migrate across the new tissue to form a barrier between the wound and the environment. Basal Keratinocytes from the wound edges and dermal appendages such as hair follicles, sweat glands and sebaceous (oil) glands are the main cells responsible for the epithelialization phase of wound healing. They advance in a sheet across the wound site and proliferate at its edges, ceasing movement when they meet in the middle.

CONTRACTION:

Around a week after wounding takes place, fibroblasts have differentiated into myofibroblasts and the wound begins to contract. In full thickness wounds, contraction peaks at 5 to 15 days post wounding. Contraction can last for several weeks and continues even after the wound is completely re-epithelialized. If contraction continues for too long, it can lead to disfigurement and loss of function.

Contraction occurs in order to reduce the size of the wound. A large wound can become 40 to 80% smaller after contraction. Wounds can contract at a speed of up to 0.75mm per day, depending on how loose the tissue in the wounded area is. Contraction usually does not occur symmetrically; rather most wounds have an 'axis of contraction' which allows for greater organization and alignment of cells with collagen. At first, contraction occurs without myofibroblasts involvement. Later, fibroblasts stimulated by growth factors differentiate into myofibroblasts. Myofibroblasts, which are similar to smooth muscle cells, are responsible for contraction. Myofibroblasts are attracted by fibronectin and growth factors and they move along fibronectin linked to fibrin in the provisional ECM in order to reach the wound edges. They form connections to the ECM at the wound edges, and they attach to each other and in the wound edges by desmosomes. Also, at an adhesion called the fibro-nexus, actin in the myofibroblasts is linked across the cell membrane to molecules in the extracellular matrix like fibronectin and collagen.

Myofibroblasts have many such adhesions, which allow them to pull the ECM when they contract, reducing the wound size. In this part of contraction, closure occurs more quickly than in the first, myofibroblasts-independent part.

As the actin in myofibroblasts contracts, the wound edges are pulled together. Fibroblasts lay down collagen to reinforce the wound as myofibroblasts contract. The contraction stage in proliferation ends as myofibroblasts stop contracting and commit apoptosis. The breakdown of the provisional matrix leads to a decrease in hyaluronic acid and an increase in chondroitin sulfate, which gradually triggers fibroblasts to stop migrating and proliferating. These events signal the onset of the maturation stage of wound healing.⁴²

FIGURE 03: PROLIFERATIVE PHASE OF WOUND HEALING

d. MATURATION AND REMODELLING PHASE

When the levels of collagen production and degradation equalize, the maturation phase of tissue repair is said to have begun. The maturation phase can last for a year or longer, depending on the size of the wound and whether it was initially closed or left open. During maturation, type III collagen, which is prevalent during proliferation, is gradually degraded and the stronger type I collagen is laid down in its place. Originally disorganized collagen fibers are rearranged, cross-linked, and aligned along tension lines. As the phase progresses, the tensile strength of the wound increases with the strength approaching 50% that of normal tissue by three months after injury and ultimately becoming as much as 80% as strong as normal tissue. Since activity at the wound site is reduced, the scar loses its red appearance as blood vessels that are no longer needed are removed by apoptosis.⁴³

FIGURE 04: MATURATION AND REMODELLING PHASE OF WOUND HEALING.

NEED AND SCOPE OF POLYHERBAL FORMULATION

From the past few years, mankind suffered a lot of adverse effects by the use of synthetic drugs. Thus, the time has come, we must pay serious attention towards natural resources which is safe to use.

Even though we have reached the 21st century, wound healing continues to be worrisome status in many places. But advanced treatments through medicinal plants are fixing them faster than ever. **Now a day's medicines with poly herbs are getting more influenced in order to achieve extra therapeutic effectiveness**, this study was carried out to evaluate the wound healing potential of Methanolic extract of polyherbal ointment containing leaves of different species of Hibiscus plant (*Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* and *Hibiscus Panduriformis*) in Wistar rats.

The medicinal use of plants is very old. The people have a long history of traditional plant usage for medicinal purposes. Traditional medicine has remained as the most affordable and easily accessible source of treatment in the primary health care system of resource especially for poor communities.

Medicinal plants are resources of new drugs and many of the modern medicines are produced indirectly from plants. It is estimated that there are more than 250,000 flower plant species. Studying medicinal plants helps to understand plant toxicity and protect human and animals from natural poisons.

In this topic the objective is to consider the past and present value of medicinal plants against wound healing activity (Plants such as (*Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* and *Hibiscus Panduriformis*)) which were used in traditional and modern medical practices as bioactive natural compounds.

Plant kingdom consists of number of medicinal plants claimed to be useful for wound healing. To promote the proper use of herbal medicine and to determine the potential as sources for new drugs, it is essential to study medicinal plants which have folklore reputation in a more intensified way.

INTRODUCTION TO SELECTED PLANTS:

1)PIANT – 01: *HIBISCUS ROSA-SINENSIS*:

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis (shoe flower) is a perennial shrub belonging to the family Malvaceae and genus Hibiscus. The genus Hibiscus contains about 275 species, which are native to tropical and south Asia and are widely distributed in different regions of world. Many Hibiscus species are mostly cultivated as ornamental plants.⁴⁴ They produce vibrantly colored showy flowers, throughout the year. Various cultivars having flowers (single or double) in shades of red, peach, white, pink, and orange are available.⁴⁵ Flowers morphology suggests the pollination through sunbirds and hummingbirds which are attracted towards nectar producing flowers. *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* is known by different names depending where you are in the world. It is known as *Bent EL-Kunsil* (Arabic), *Rosa della Cina* (Italian), *Aka-bana* (Japanese), *Shoe flower* (English), *Japa* (Sanskrit), *Jasum* (Hindi, Punjabi), *Hibiscus de Chine* (China), *Joba* (Bengali), *Java* (Telugu), *Chinesischer Roseneibisch* (German), *Clavel japonés* (Spanish), *Hibiscus* (Swedish) and *Gudhal* (Urdu).⁴⁶

History:

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis is probably originated from India. Old Moorish (Arabs) believe that it is originated from Spain. Many others claim that *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* is a collection of man-made hybrids and is not a natural herb. Hibiscus word is derived from Greed word "hibiskos" meaning white or marshmallow.

Demography/Location:

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis is highly sensitive to frost and freeze in mild cold conditions. It shows best growth in full sun and well drained soil rich in organic matter. It is widely distributed in following countries: India (south western regions), Sri-Lanka (tropical regions), Thailand, South Africa, Phillipines, Myanmar, China and Pakistan.

Botany / Morphology:

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis is a perennial shrub having tap root system. Its leaves are 3 to 12cm long and 2 to 5cm wide. Leaves are simply ovate or lanceolate which are entire at the base and coarsely toothed at the tip/margins. Flowers are actinomorphic, pedicellate, complete, and pentamerous. Corolla contains five petals and is 3 inches in diameter.⁴⁷ A

number of varieties differing in color and size of corolla are available. Fruit is a capsule having length of 3cm and forms very rarely.⁴⁸ *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* show best growth in well-drained and slightly acidic soils. In sandy soils, it uses fully decomposed organic matter to maintain water holding capacity, aeration and drainage of the soil. Plants require full sunlight because inadequate light limits flowering. However, they can tolerate partial shade.

FIGURE 05: Image of *Hibiscus rosa sinensis*

2) PLANT – 02: HIBISCUS PANDURIFORMIS
Hibiscus panduriformis Burm.f., popularly called as ‘Yellow Hibiscus’, is widely distributed in tropical Africa, Madagascar and tropical Asia. It occurs from sea level up to 2000 m altitude in the woodland and grassland, alluvial clay flats, riverbanks, roadsides, cultivated land and fallows. It also grows as a weed on black soil, in dry sandy places, often in places of old cultivation and disturbed areas. The plant is mainly utilised by local people as a source of fibre and as ornamental plant.⁴⁹

FIGURE 06: Image of *Hibiscus panduriformis*.

METHODOLOGY AND RESULT:

PLANT COLLECTION and DRYING (Under shade):

The leaves of *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* and *Hibiscus Panduriformis* were collected from the local fields of Gulbarga (Gulbarga university) washed with tap water to remove the dust and soil. The whole plant was dried under shade, powdered and made to pass through sieve No. 40 meshes and stored in closed vessel. The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by Miss Rasika S Kapale, HOD, Department of Botany, Smt V G Degree College for Women's, Gulbarga. Karnataka. India.

A voucher specimen no. HKES/VGC/BOT/18

Figure 07: Collection of plants by authors (Varunkumar, Bhimabai.D, Arshiya naaz, Sonali vilas badganchi and Nikita Sanjeev)

Figure 08: Preparation of herbarium of plants.

Figure 09: Submission of herbarium to Department of Botany, VG Womens govt college.

	H. K. E. Society's SMT. VEERAMMA GANGASIRI COLLEGE FOR WOMEN NAAC Accredited 'A' Grade - website : www.vgcollege.in KALABURAGI - 585 102 DEPARTMENT OF BOTANY		
Ref. No. : HKES/VGC/BOT/	Date : 04/08/2025		
<u>Authentic Certificate</u>			
<p>This is to certify that Miss. Arshiya Naaz of Aryan college of Pharmacy Kalaburagi has submitted specimen Hibiscus rosa- sinesis belongs to Malvaceae family. Hence, in view of this, I do here by inform you that plant part submitted by you is found very good matches in its characters, after proper examination with the help of Karnataka flora and Gulbarga district flora.</p>			
<p>I do here by recommend as such plant is Authentic and be used for further research project.</p>			
SI.NO No.	Name of the Plant	Family	SVGWC
18	Hibiscus rosa- sinesis	Malvaceae	18
 Miss. Rasika S Kapale Head Dept. of Botany Smt. V.G. Govt College for Women KALABURAGI			

Figure 10: Authentication Certificate.

Preparation of Plant Extracts:

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis and *Hibiscus Panduriformis* was collected and shade dried, powdered in a mixer and sieved, powder of required particle size was obtained (sieve no 40).

The 500gm of polyherbal homogeneous powder material was extracted in Soxhlet using methanol as solvent for 48 hours. The filtrate is collected and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure using an evaporator (Rotary flash). The extracts obtained was weighed from each solvent; its percentage was calculated in terms of air-dried weight of plants materials. The dried extracts were preserved at 4°C in small sterilized containers, for further use.

Figure 11: Preparation of Methanolic extract of selected plants.

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF EXTRACTS.

Figure 12: Performing of chemical tests by authors.

Figure 13: Performing of chemical tests by authors.**Table 01: Result of chemical tests.**

Sl.no	Phytochemical constituents	Methanolic extract
01	Alkaloids	+
02	Flavonoid	+++
03	Tannin	++
04	Terpenoid	+
05	Glycoside	+
06	Saponin	+++
07	Carbohydrates	+
08	Proteins	+
09	Amino acids	+
10	Steroid	++
11	Gums	-

INCISION WOUND MODEL ON RATS⁵⁰⁻⁵⁸

The rats were anesthetized prior to and during the creation of wound the dorsal fur of the animals was shaved with an electric clipper. A longitudinal paravertebral incision, six centimeters in length was made through the skin and cutaneous muscle on the back as described by Ehrlich and hunt *et al*. After the incision, surgical sutures were applied to the parted skin at intervals of one centimeter. The wounds were left undressed.

The animals were randomly divided into 6 groups and each group containing 6 animals. The treatments of each ointment were applied topically once a day.

- 1. Group I** : Control group
- 2. Group II** : Test group Treated with Polyherbal formulation
- 3. Group III** : Mupirocin (Reference Standard)

The sutures were removed on 8th post wounding day and the treatment was continued. The wound breaking strength was measured on the tenth day by the method described by Lee.

Figure 14: Suturing of wound.**DETERMINATION OF WOUND BREAKING STRENGTH:**

The anesthetized animals were secured to the table, and a line was drawn on either side of the wound 3mm away from the line. This line was gripped using forceps one at each end opposed to each other. One of the forceps was supported firmly, were as the other was connected to a freely suspended light weight metal plate. Weight was added slowly and the gradual increase in weight, pulling apart the

wound edges. As the wound just opened up, addition of weight was stopped and the weights added was noted as a measure of breaking strength in grams. Three readings were recorded for a given incision wound. The mean reading for the group was taken as an individual value of breaking strength⁵⁹⁻⁶⁵. The results were analysed by one way Anova followed by dunnet's t test.

Table 02: EFFECTS OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT ON SELECTED POLY HERBAL PLANTS ON INCISION WOUND MODEL:

Group	BREAKING STRENGTH OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF POLYHERBAL FORMULATION
Control	125.55±2.01
Methanolic extract	311.45±3.91
Mupirocine	322.60±4.00

Figure 16: Breaking of wound by pulling force of breaking strength**DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:**

The wound healing activity was evaluated by incision wound model in wistar rats. In the incision wound model, the tensile strength of the new generated tissue was measured. Collagen, the major protein of the extracellular matrix, is the component that ultimately liberates free hydroxyproline and its peptides. The tensile strength of a wound is determined by the rate of collagen synthesis and more so, by the maturation process where there is a covalent binding of collagen fibrils through inter and intra molecular cross linking. It was found that the tensile strength of new tissue was more in the treated groups with least significant signs of infection. The strength of the tissues was statistically significant in the polyherbal topical group. However, the results were most encouraging and statistically significant in the topically treated polyherbal formulations. The wound healing studies revealed that the polyherbal formulation possess significant activity so it is

concluded that the polyherbal topical formulations has got remarkable results in incision wound healing model.

REFERENCES:

1. Verma. S. and Singh. S.P. Current and future status of herbal medicines. *Veterinary world*. 2008; 1 (11): 347 – 350.
2. James. O and Victoria. I.A. Excision and Incision wound healing potential of *Saba florida* (Benth) leaf extract in *rattus norvegicus*. *International journal on pharmaceutical and biomedical research*. 2010; 1(4): 101 – 107.
3. Bhagwat. D.A, Killedar. S.G and Adnaik. R.S. Antidiabetic activity of leaf extract of *Tridax procumbens*. *International journal of green pharmacy*. 2008; 2(2): 126 – 128.
4. Kamboj. V.P. Herbal medicine. *Current science*. 2000; 78(1): 35 – 39.
5. Nayak. S, Nalabothu. P, Sandiford. S, Bhogadi.

- V and Adogw. A. Evaluation of Wound healing activity of *Allamanda cathartica*. L. And *Laurus nobilis*. L. extracts on rats. BioMed Central Complementary and Alternative Medicine, 2006; 6: 12.
6. Kodati. DR, Burra. S and Kumar GP. Evaluation of wound healing activity of Methanolic root extract of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. in wistar albino rats. Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research. 2011; 1(2): 26-34.
 7. Khan Mohammed N. The influence of diabetes on wound healing. Online. URL: <http://www.gale.com>. Cited 2005 sep 22.
 8. Ambrish C, Torgal SS, Patil PA, Malur PR, Hiremath SV. Influence of oral antidiabetic agents on wound healing in euglycemic male wistar rats. Pharmacology online, 2009; 1: 476 – 483.
 9. Shivananda Nayak. Influence of Methanolic extract of *Vinca rosea* on wound healing in diabetic rats. Online Journal of Biological Sciences 2006; 6 (2): 40 – 44.
 10. Hope over diabetes wound healing. Online available from: URL: <http://www.BBCNewsPaper>. Cited 2006 March 18.
 11. Elizebeth. E by. Wound care and cleansing. Online. Available from. URL: <http://www.access2wellness.com>. 2009 Aug 20.
 12. Sharma Y, Jeyabalan G, Singh R, Semwal A. Current Aspects of Wound Healing Agents from Medicinal Plants: A Review. Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies. (Online Available at www.plantsjournal.com). 2013; 1(3): 1 – 11.
 13. Sabiston. D.C. (ed.): Textbook of Surgery, W.B. Saunders Co., Philadelphia, PA. 1972; 300.
 14. Siegal. B, Adam. Y and Oland. Y. Blessures de guerre et infections. Etude comparative des blessures chez les combattants israeliens et egyptiens de la guerre d'octobre. 1976.
 15. Guerre de Kippour. Ann. Chir. 1973; 30, 10, 781.
 16. Robbins & Cotran. Pathological basis of disease. 2010; 8: 3.
 17. Dr. Intire. RS. Tissue renewal, repair, & regeneration. 2008: 100-108.
 18. Hess. CT. Clinical Guide to Skin and Wound Care. 6th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. Advances in Skin & Wound Care. 2011; 24(4): 192.
 19. Kirsner. RS and Eaglstein WH. The wound healing process. Dermatol Clin 1993; 11: 629-40.
 20. Grinnell. F, Billingham RE, Burgess L. Distribution of fibronectin during wound healing in vivo. Journal of Invest Dermatol 1981; 76: 181- 9.
 21. Tortora. G.J, Grabowski. S.R. Principles of Anatomy and Physiology. New York. Harper Collins College Publications, 1996; 8.
 22. Winter. G and Scales. J.T. Effect of air drying and dressings on the surface of a wound. Nature 1963; 5: 91-92.
 23. Krasnor. D. Chronic Wound Care. A clinical sourcebook for healthcare professionals. Wayne, Pa: Health Management Publications, 1996: 2.
 24. Flanagan. M. Wound Management. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone, 1997.
 25. Bennett. G and Moody. M. Wound Care for Health Professionals. London: Chapman and Hall, 1995.
 26. Hutchinson. J.J. Prevalence of wound infection under occlusive dressings: a collective survey of reported research. Wounds 1989; 1: 123-133.
 27. Katz. M.H, Alvarez. A.F, Kirsner. R.S, et al. Human wound fluid from acute wounds stimulates fibroblasts and endothelial cell growth. Journal Am Academic Derma 1991; 25: 1054-1058.
 28. Clark. R.A.F. Overview and general considerations of wound repair. The Molecular and Cellular Biology of Wound Repair. New York: Plenum, 1988.
 29. Nathan. C.F. Secretory products of macrophages. Journal Clin Investigation 1987; 79:319-326.
 30. Baxter. C.R. Immunologic reactions in chronic wounds. Am J Surgery 1994; 167: 12 - 14.
 31. Robson. M.C. The role of growth factors in the healing of chronic wounds. Wound Repair and Regeneration 1997; 5: 12-17.
 32. Robson. M.C. The role of growth factors in the healing of chronic wounds. Wound Repair and Regeneration. 1997; 5: 11.
 33. Knighton. D, et al. Regulation of wound healing angiogenesis: effect of oxygen gradients and inspired oxygen concentration. Surgery 1981; 90: 262-270.
 34. Harding. K, Cutting. K. Criteria for identifying wound infection. Journal Wound Care 1994; 3 (4): 198-201.
 35. Brown. G.L. Acceleration of tensile strength of incisions treated with EGF and TGF. Annals of Surgery 1988; 208:788-794.
 36. Winter. G. Formulation of the scab and the rate of epithelialization in the skin of the domestic pig. Nature 1962; 193: 293-294.
 37. Lock. P. The Effects of Temperature on Mitotic Activity at the Edge of Experimental Wounds. Lock Research Laboratories Paper. Kent: Lock Laboratories, 1979.
 38. Myers. J.A. Wound healing and the use of a modern surgical dressing. Pharmaceutical J 1982; 2: 103-104.
 39. Garrett. B. Re-epithelialization. Journal Wound

- Care 1998; 7(7): 358-359.
40. Whitby. D.J, Ferguson. M.W. Immuno Histochemical Localisation of growth factors in foetal healing. *Developing Biology* 1991; 147: 207-215.
 41. Eisenbeiss. W, Peter. P.W, Bakhtiari. C, *et al.* Hypertrophic scars and keloids. *Journal Wound Care* 1998; 7(5): 255-257.
 42. Fincham Gee. C. Nutrition and wound healing. *Nursing* 1990; 4(18): 26-28.
 43. Kiecolt-Glaser. J.K, Marucha. P.T, Malarkey. W.B, *et al.* Slowing of wound healing by psychological stress. *Lancet* 1995; 346: 1194-1196.
 44. J. Lowry. (1976). Floral anthocyanins of some Malesian Hibiscus species. *Phytochemistry*. 15(9): 1395-1396.
 45. E.F. Gilman. (1999). *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*. Institute of Food and Agricultural Science, University of Floryda. 254.
 46. A.E. Al-Snafi. (2018). Chemical constituents, pharmacological effects and therapeutic importance of Hibiscus rosa-sinensis-A review. *Journal of Pharmacy*. 8(7): 101-119.
 47. K. Rao, K. Geetha, D. Banji. (2014). Quality control study and standardization of Hibiscus rosasinensis L. flowers and leaves as per WHO guidelines. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 3(4).
 48. I.A. Ross, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*. In *Medicinal Plants of the World*, Springer: 2003; pp 253-266.
 49. Mishra *etal.* *Hibiscus Panduriformis* Burm. F. (*Malvaceae*): A new distributional record from Odisha. *E-Planet*. 2020; 18(2): 142-144.
 50. B. S. Nayak and Lexley M Pinto Pereira. *Catharanthus roseus* flower extract has wound healing activity in Sprague Dawley rats. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 2006; 6: 41.
 51. Dash GK, Mondal S, Murty PN. Evaluation of wound healing effects of Argemone mexicana Linn. Leaves. *Herbal Heritage*. 2009; 136-141.
 52. Lee KH. Studies on mechanism of action of salicylates II. Retardation of wound healing by aspirin. *Journal Pharm Sci*. 1968; 1042-1043.
 53. A.O.A.C. Official methods of analysis. Assoc. Official Agricultural Chemists, Washington DC. 10th ed.
 54. Gray H, Williams PL, Bannister LH, Berry MN. Gray's anatomy: The anatomical basis of medicine and surgery. New York (NY): Churchill Livingstone; 1995: 412, 417.
 55. H.Paul Ehrlich. M. A. Thomas K, Hunt M.D. Effect of cortisone and vitamine A on wound healing. *Annals of surgery* 1968; 167: 324-328.
 56. Peacock EE, Cohen IK. Wound healing. In: McCarthy JG May JW, Littler JW, editors. *Plastic surgery*. Philadelphia (PA): W.B. Saunders Company; 1990; 1: 161-85.
 57. Manjunath. B. K, *et al.* wound healing activity of *Lycopodium Serratum*. *Indian Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2007; 69 (2): 283-287.
 58. Martin P. Wound healing-aiming for perfect skin regeneration. *Science*. 1997; 276:75-81.
 59. Verma. N, *et al.* wound healing activity of *Wededia Chinensis* leaves. *Pharmacology online* 2008; 2:139-145.
 60. Carter, J. S. Muscle Tissue. Retrieved from Clermont College, University of Cincinnati. <http://biology.clc.uc.edu//muscles.htm>. 1996.
 61. Albright A. L and Stern. J.S. Adipose Tissue. Retrieved from Department of nutrition and Internal medicine, University of California. <http://www.sportsci.org//.html>. 1998.
 62. King, D. Connective Tissue Study Guide. Retrieved from school of medicine, Southern Illinois University. <http://biology.clc.uc.edu//.htm>. 2010.
 63. Lai, S.Y. Suture Selection. Sutures and Needles, 1-4. Retrieved from <http://emedicine.medscape.com//overview>. 2011: 8.
 64. Martell. J, Elmr. T, Gopalsami. N and Park. Y.S. Visual measurement of suture strain for robotic surgery. *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine*, 2011; 10: 11 55.
 65. Suzuki, A.R. (n.d). Overall strength of various suture techniques in Wound Closure. Retrieved from <http://www.usc.edu/////pdf>.